

1 **Complete genomes of *Priestia megaterium* and *Enterobacter ludwigii*: Non-symbiotic**
2 **endophytes from algerian cowpea nodules**

3 **Nadjette Djemouai^{1,2}, Dif Guendouz^{2,3}, Saadia Ouled Amrane⁴, Khadidja Oulad Hadj**
4 **Youcef⁵, Bakelli Aissa¹, Baali Faiza¹, Kathia Belaid^{6,7}**

5 ¹ Département de Biologie, Faculté des Sciences de la Nature et de la Vie et Sciences de la
6 Terre, Université de Ghardaia, 47000 Ghardaïa, Algeria

7 ² Laboratoire de Biologie des Systèmes Microbiens (LBSM), Ecole Normale Supérieure Cheikh
8 Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi, BP 92, Kouba, Algiers, Algeria

9 ³ École Normale Supérieure Taleb Abderrahmane de Laghouat, Département des Sciences
10 Naturelles, BP 4033, Laghouat 03000, Algeria

11 ⁴ Scientific Research Station of the Biological Sciences Station at Belbachir, El Menia, Algeria.

12 ⁵ Applied Research Unit for Renewable Energies (URAER), Renewable Energy Development
13 Center (CDER), Ghardaïa, Algeria

14 ⁶ Laboratory of Biology and Physiology of Organisms (LBPO), Biological Sciences Faculty,
15 Houari Boumediene Sciences and Technology University (USTHB), El-Alia, Bab Ezzouar,
16 Algiers, Algeria

17 ⁷ Department of Biology, Faculty of Nature, Life Sciences and Earth Sciences, University of
18 Bouira-Akli Mohand Oulhadj, Bouira, Algeria

19 **Corresponding author:** Nadjette Djemouai (djemouai.nadjette@univ-ghardaia.dz)

20 **Abstract**

21 This study reports the isolation and whole-genome sequencing of three non-symbiotic,
22 nitrogen-fixing bacterial strains recovered from root nodules of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*)
23 grown in a Saharan environment. Although associated with legume nodules, these strains are
24 non-symbiotic but still capable of nitrogen fixation. Whole-genome sequence analysis assigned
25 the isolates to *Priestia megaterium* (2 strains) and *Enterobacter* (1 strain) species, revealing the
26 presence of genes related to nitrogen metabolism and plant growth promotion. The
27 identification of free-living or non-symbiotic diazotrophs within cowpea nodules highlights the
28 complexity of the nodule microbiome and suggests a potential role of these bacteria in
29 enhancing nitrogen availability and plant performance under Saharan conditions.

30 **Key words:** *Vigna unguiculata*, nodules, WGS, Desert, *Priestia*, *Enterobacter*

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32 **Introduction**

33 Legume root nodules are classically regarded as specialized organs hosting symbiotic
34 nitrogen-fixing rhizobia, such as *Bradyrhizobium*, *Rhizobium*, and *Ensifer*, which reduce
35 atmospheric nitrogen into ammonia in exchange for plant-derived carbon (Coba de la Peña et
36 al., 2018). However, recent studies have shown that nodules also harbor a diverse microbiome,
37 including non-symbiotic or endophytic bacteria that are not essential for nodule formation but
38 may contribute to nitrogen acquisition and plant growth (Santoyo, 2022). In particular, several
39 free-living and nodule-associated diazotrophs have been reported to fix nitrogen independently
40 of the canonical symbiotic system, adding a supplementary layer of nitrogen input in
41 legume-based cropping systems (Bellenger et al., 2014; Ladha et al., 2022).

42 Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) is a drought-tolerant legume widely cultivated in arid and
43 semi-arid regions, including the Sahara, where low soil fertility and water scarcity limit crop
44 productivity (Kim et al., 2025). In such environments, biological nitrogen fixation becomes a
45 key strategy to sustain production without relying heavily on chemical fertilizers (Soumare et
46 al., 2020). While symbiotic rhizobia are well-documented in cowpea nodules, less is known
47 about the diversity and functional role of non-symbiotic nitrogen-fixing bacteria inhabiting
48 these structures (Klepa et al., 2022; Mbah et al., 2022; Yohannes et al., 2024). Evidence
49 suggests that members of genera such as *Priestia* and *Enterobacter* can colonize root nodules
50 as endophytes or opportunistic associates, where they may contribute to nitrogen fixation and
51 other plant growth-promoting traits (Zhu et al., 2025).

52 In this context, we report the isolation of four non-symbiotic nitrogen-fixing bacterial strains
53 from root nodules of cowpea plants grown in a Saharan environment. Whole-genome
54 sequencing assigned these isolates to *Priestia megaterium* and *Enterobacter* species, revealing
55 genomic features associated with nitrogen metabolism and adaptation to arid conditions. This
56 study aims to characterize these nodule-associated diazotrophs and to explore their potential
57 contribution to nitrogen nutrition and plant growth in dryland agricultural systems, highlighting
58 the importance of non-symbiotic bacteria within the legume nodule microbiome.

59 **Material and Methods**

60 **1. Sample collection and isolation**

61 Nodules of *Vigna unguiculata* were collected from plants growing at three different localities
62 within El Golea province, Algeria. Cowpea plants grown at the Université des Sciences et de la
63 Technologie Houari Boumediene (USTHB) experimental field station, Hassi Ghanem
64 (El-Golea) and Hofra region in El-Golea oasis were collected. First, nodules were carefully

65 detached from the root system, placed in sterile polyethylene bags, and transported to the
66 laboratory in an icebox. Samples were processed within 24 h of collection.

67 The bacteria were isolated from surface-sterilized nodules using the suspension dilution
68 method. A 10^{-3} dilution was prepared in sterile saline solution, and 100 μ L of this dilution was
69 plated onto yeast extract–mannitol (YEM) medium supplemented with the antifungal agent
70 cycloheximide at 50 μ g/mL. Plates were incubated at 28 ± 2 °C for 10 days. Distinct bacterial
71 colonies were selected, purified by successive streaking, and designated as isolates VA1, VA7,
72 and VA9. Glycerol stocks of each purified isolate were prepared and stored at -20 °C for
73 long-term conservation.

74 **3. Whole-genome sequencing of bacteria**

75 The genomic DNA of the three strains was processed by MicrobesNG. The libraries were
76 constructed employing the Nextera XT kit (Illumina) on a Hamilton Microlab STAR system.
77 Sequencing was ran on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) utilising a 250
78 bp paired-end technique. Reads underwent adapter trimming using Trimmomatic v0.30 (Bolger
79 et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality threshold of Q15. De novo assembly was conducted
80 with SPAdes v3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs were annotated with Prokka v1.11
81 (Seemann, 2014).

82 **Results**

83 **Genome sequencing and assembly quality**

84 Three bacterial endophyte strains (VA1, VA7, VA9) isolated from healthy cowpea root nodules
85 underwent whole-genome sequencing, yielding high-quality assemblies (Table
86 1). VA1 (SAMN57186234) and VA7 (SAMN56134205), both identified as *Priestia*
87 *megaterium*, produced near-complete genomes of 5.86 Mb and 5.71 Mb, respectively, with
88 identical 37.5% GC content, 38-49 contigs (≥ 1 kb), N_{50} values of 969.5 kb, and excellent
89 coverage (62.6 \times -86.6 \times). On the other hand, VA9 (SAMN56001665), identified
90 as *Enterobacter ludwigii*, generated a smaller, high-GC (54.5%) genome (4.75 Mb, 19 contigs,
91 780.5 kb N_{50} , 56.2 \times coverage).

92 All assemblies met stringent quality standards for comparative genomics ($N_{50} > 780$ kb, < 50
93 contigs, $> 50\times$ coverage), enabling comprehensive functional annotation. Complete assemblies
94 were deposited in GenBank: GCA_056786235.1 (VA1), GCA_055710015.1 (VA7),
95 GCA_055759495.1 (VA9), with raw reads SRR38049304, SRR38067822, and SRR38067821.
96 These strains establish a foundation for defined consortium formulation, stability testing, and
97 comparative transcriptomics during *Vigna* colonization, critical steps toward commercial
98 microbial inoculant development for sustainable legume production. Additionally, mining these

99 genomes will elucidate the molecular interactions enabling non-symbiotic bacterial nodule
100 colonization in cowpea, expanding understanding of beneficial plant-microbe associations
101 beyond rhizobial symbiosis.

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103 **Table 1.** Summary statistics for the genomes studied

Bcterial strain	Biosample	Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	Largest contig	Total length	GC (%)	Mean coverage	<i>N</i> ₅₀	CDS	tRNA	rRNA	GenBank accession (Assembly)	GenBank accession (reads)
VA1	SAMN57186234	49	1251898	5864871	37.5	62.5635x	969.5 kb	6,066	128	58	GCA_056786235.1	SRR38049304
VA7	SAMN56134205	38	1253776	5713152	37.5	86.5636x	969.5 kb	5,898	111	55	GCA_055710015.1	SRR38067822
VA9	SAMN56001665	19	830146	4748790	54.5	56.2218x	780.5 kb	4,602	77	29	GCA_055759495.1	SRR38067821

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